

Determinants of regional development and their impact on electoral processes

Florentina Chirodea¹, Mihai Ion Marian² and Delia Georgeta Bekesi³

Abstract

Regional development, a process with multiple economic, social and environmental facets, is determined by a complex interaction of factors that shape its trajectory. Development models are intrinsically linked to local history, the strategic use of existing resources, the cultivation of economic opportunities and the enhancement of human capital, and their application often generates contradictory results. The determinants of regional development vary in type, some of which are considered essential in economic, social and territorial cohesion policy due to the extent to which they can influence social values and collective aspirations. A wealth of specialist literature also highlights their influence on electoral processes, party strategies and election results. In this context, the study aims to identify the main categories of factors determining the development process in a region and how they shape the preferences of voters in four counties belonging to the North-West Development Region (Bihor, Sălaj, Satu Mare, and Maramureș). The analysis focuses on the second round of the presidential elections in Romania and aims to highlight the behavior of those who voted on 18 May 2025, compared to that defined by Dumitru Sandu in 2014.

Keywords

Regional development; presidential elections; determining factors

¹ Florentina Chirodea (ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7647-709X>), PhD in History (2011), is an Associate Professor at the Department of International Relations and European Studies (DIREs) at University of Oradea, coordinator of Jean Monnet Module Development of the Border Regions in Central and Eastern European Countries (2018-2021). Her research interests include the development of the border region, sustainability, and social responsibility. E-mail: mmarian@uoradea.ro.

² Mihai Ion Marian (ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7647-709X>), PhD in Psychology, is an Associate Professor at the Department of Psychology at University of Oradea. He is the editor of the Journal of Psychological and Educational Research and of the International Journal of Education and Psychology in Community. E-mail: mmarian@uoradea.ro.

³ Delia Georgeta Bekesi (ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7896-637X>), PhD in Sociology, is an Assistant Professor at University of Oradea. Her research interests include labor market, sustainable development, human resources management, microeconomics, and personnel wages. E-mail: g.bekesi@uoradea.ro.

Introduction

Development, a complex process with multiple dimensions and meanings, is a concept often associated with the notion of change, advancement, evolution, progress, or modernization, all of which imply planned transformations through which a particular socio-economic context becomes better. Because the results are noticeable in the medium and long term, this concept also has a strategic connotation, which political parties often place at the center of their doctrines. Development involves complex and profound changes within communities, so as development theories have evolved, the number of indicators reflecting progress has become increasingly large.

The transformations were most visible around the 1950s, as theoretical models of development were based solely on increasing production through industrialization and investment in human capital (Peet and Hartwick, 2015), raising income levels and increasing per capita production (Lewis, 1955; Baran, 1957). A decade later, the UN introduced the social dimension into the concept of development (Esteva, 2010: 8-10), and ECOSOC recommended striking a balance between the two processes, given the interdependence between the classic system of indicators - GDP, labor productivity, velocity of money, trade balance, etc. (Sciarelli and Rinaldi, 2017: 34), and those established in 1972 by the World Bank for basic human needs - nutrition, shelter, health, literacy and work (Maddux, 1981: 18). In 1975, UNESCO added a human-centered dimension, promoting an integrated definition of the concept of development that also included aspects related to community life and human relations with the outside world and with one's own conscience (Esteva, 2010: 11). This was followed by the efforts of the UN World Commission on Environment and Development to ensure a common future for all nations and to introduce the dimension of sustainability into all actions aimed at socio-economic and human progress (UN, 2017).

Therefore, at the end of the 20th century, the latest development models mentioned as major factors for economic and social progress in a democratic society: ensuring a basic level of well-being on a large scale and respecting the principle of human freedom (Sen, 1993: 30-53); technological progress and human capital formation (Putnam, 1994); the existence of social capital and cooperative relationships between individuals with common goals (Fukuyama, 1995). In the 21st century, development encompasses even more aspects of social life, the aim being to establish as complete a picture as possible of the results of joint actions to achieve a desirable state in a country/region/community, following a process planned over time (Zamfir, 2006: 11). Development, as a concept, was defined at the beginning of the third millennium through the Millennium Development Goals (UN, 2000), and subsequently, as transformations become increasingly complex, it encompasses other dimensions highlighted by the UN in 2015 through the 17 Global Sustainable Development Goals - SDGs (UN, 2016).

By reporting these dimensions and all indicators that define ODRs for a specific, well-defined area, we can obtain a picture of sustainable development and the socio-economic context at the micro-level (towns, villages, metropolitan areas, counties, other NUTS III regions), meso- (NUTS II development regions) or macro-regional (the territory of a state or the entire European Union), depending on the classification of the administrative unit analyzed in the Common Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics. The scientific field that studies the relationship between electoral behavior and its context is electoral geography. Specialists in this field have highlighted the fact that, within a geographical area, the distribution of votes is influenced by various historical, economic, cultural, identity and educational factors. The way voters perceive socio-economic realities at a given moment determines their preferences for different political parties (Gabor, 2025: 53). Thus, economic conditions act as a barometer of public sentiment, with economic crises, sudden variations in economic

indicators or economic recessions often accompanied by increased voter dissatisfaction. This can change voter turnout or bring about changes in political loyalty (Pattie et al, 2015).

In 2014, Ansolabehere et al. conducted a study analyzing how personal economic experiences influence electoral choices. Their results suggest that individuals' perceptions of economic conditions, rather than economic indicators, are more important: voters who perceive their financial situation as deteriorating are more likely to support candidates who advocate economic reform or economic assistance (Ansolabehere, Meredith and Snowberg, 2014). A year later, Soroka et al. examined data from several countries over several electoral cycles and developed a microeconomic voting model, according to which economic slowdowns lead to increased dissatisfaction with ruling parties and increased support for opposition parties. The analysis indicates that changes in GDP, unemployment and inflation can generate shifts in public opinion, especially at the end of an electoral cycle (Soroka, Stecula and Wlezien, 2015).

Gavazza et al. also explore the ramifications of economic trends after the 2008 financial crisis on electoral behavior in the 2015 general election in the United Kingdom. The analysis indicates that the areas most severely affected by austerity measures saw a marked shift in favor of populist parties. Areas with higher unemployment rates and reduced public services showed a distinct tendency to favor parties that could articulate a message of national sovereignty and economic revival. The authors point out that voters do not simply respond to declining indicators of economic prosperity but rather interpret these conditions through the lens of their life experiences, further complicating the relationship between economic performance and political loyalty (Gavazza, Nardotto, and Valletti, 2019). Essletzbichler, Disslbacher, and Moser attribute another cause of the rise in populist voting to the social marginalization that has emerged as a result of neoliberal globalization. The study highlights the growing importance of economic insecurity in how voters seek a representative political actor who responds to their dissatisfaction (Essletzbichler, Disslbacher and Moser, 2018).

Different social contexts from one area to another can lead to variable electoral behavior, as different groups prioritize different issues depending on their life experiences and social positioning. The alignment of social interests with economic conditions can generate coalition dynamics among voters, affecting the final election results (Gavazza, Nardotto, and Valletti, 2019). Social factors further complicate voter preferences, with the relationship between electoral behavior and the political and social context in which eligible voters live being widely debated by political sociologists. Basarabă highlights the fact that in a community, the social context can influence the likelihood of social interactions between and within groups and can affect the flow of politically relevant information (Basarabă, 2015: 70) and, consequently, electoral results. Also, how demographic factors intersect with economic and social variables is important for researchers of electoral behavior, even in very small communities. For example, demographic changes can influence the electoral behavior of natives in a region where the presence of immigrants generates tensions due to competition for resources (Guglielmo et al, 2016; Altindag and Kaushal, 2021). Similarly, the migration of a significant segment of the population to societies with a high standard of living has consequences for the electoral behavior of individuals in multi-layered communities (Soare and Tufiş, 2023; Gherghina and Basarabă, 2024).

In turn, voter behavior has equally complex consequences, with election results going beyond the promotion of progressive or conservative political platforms or coalitions. The three schools of thought (Michigan, Rochester and Columbia University) that analyze electoral behavior each develop a model that focuses on a single determining factor in the decision-making process of an individual expressing their electoral preference. Combining the sociological model with the psychosocial and spatial models is a solution recommended by specialists (Sasu and Dang, 2015: 77) to reflect broader

socio-economic and all trends that have an impact on governance and public policies with a direct influence on the dynamics and structure of development processes (Simonovits, Kates, and Szeidl, 2019).

Socio-economic development processes in Romania and in the area under analysis

In Romania, socio-economic and political transformations have had significant results, although the transition to a market economy has often been marked by the failure of national macroeconomic policies, the power struggle between different political parties and alliances, and the lack of long-term vision of post-communist governments. Accession to the European Union in 2007 provided Romania with the opportunity to build a broader socio-political context, also in transition, but one in which the impact of EU policies and programs was reflected in moderate but steady growth in development indicators (Şoproni and Horga, 2015). Since 2014, Romania has achieved notable successes in integrating European funds (Brad, 2020), especially in rural infrastructure, connectivity and economic opportunities, which have led to a national GDP growth rate above the EU average (Wojciech, 2018). At the same time, budget deficits have been a challenge to maintaining this pace over a long period of time (Sorlescu, Croitoru and Dobrotă, 2024). In turn, the Romanian agricultural sector has undergone significant changes following the reform of the EU's Common Agricultural Policy, with the integration of modern practices to increase productivity and implement rural development programs (Adamyk, 2025). However, inequalities between urban and rural areas persist and deepen as strong urban centers or agglomerations emerge locally or regionally (Gormar, 2019).

From a social perspective, over the last two decades, Romania has faced challenges related to the exodus of the population from rural areas to large cities, migration to Western EU countries, an ageing population and labor shortages in various sectors. At the same time, European programs aimed at social inclusion have reduced social inequalities, especially in marginalized communities (Nagy and Durst, 2018), although Romanian society still faces prejudices that create socio-economic barriers (Florea, Gagy and Jacobsson, 2018). During the same period, the political landscape was marked by instability generated by frequent changes in government coalitions and corruption scandals (especially those revealed in 2015). These led to growing public discontent, large-scale protests and demands from civil society for accountability and transparency in government structures (Rácz and Egyed, 2023). The response of decision-makers has focused more on combating corruption and strengthening institutional integrity, sometimes limiting progress on sustainable development. In addition, the rise of populism and national sovereignty in the broader European context could have implications for the maintenance of democratic norms and Romania's alignment with European Union values (Buzogany, 2020; Popescu and Petrița, 2017).

Therefore, the transition processes in Romania are not yet complete, being shaped by a complex interaction between local and national economic, social and political factors, and will only be finalized when: the economy generates prosperity for all its citizens (Şoproni and Horga, 2015); domestic policies are aligned with European standards to facilitate a business-friendly operating environment (Drăgoi and Bâlgăr, 2015); economic growth strategies incorporate long-term environmental and social equity considerations (Keller and Virag, 2022); the gap between urban regions and less developed rural areas will be minimized through targeted interventions (Berkes et al, 2024); the sustainability of economic growth will be achieved through significant investments in green technologies and renewable energy (Draghia, 2023).

The four counties considered in the case study are part of the North-West Development Region and are located on the periphery of Brussels and Bucharest, at the intersection of Europe's

north-south and east-west axes. Two of them (Bihor and Satu Mare) have a 265 km Schengen border with Hungary to the west, while Satu Mare and Maramureș border Ukraine to the north along a 250 km stretch of border. According to the OECD classification of NUTS III regions, based on the percentage of the population living in ATUs with a population density of less than 150 inhabitants/km², the four counties fall into the following categories: predominantly rural – Maramureș and Sălaj; predominantly rural close to the city – Satu Mare; intermediate close to the city – Bihor (North-West RDA, 2021). Also, in the four counties, 70% of all towns are very small and small, and the only urban center, Oradea, has expanded massively into the metropolitan area, leading to population growth in peri-urban areas. The other three county capitals (Satu Mare, Zalău and Baia Mare) have expanded mainly through a process of suburbanization, while maintaining their administrative boundaries (North-West RDA, 2021).

In terms of the network of urban settlements, the following categories of polarized centers and dominant flows exist in the analyzed area (Bihor County Council, 2021, pp. 2019–220; Satu Mare County Council, 2021; Maramureș County Council, 2021, p. 82; Sălaj County Council, 2021, p. 261): (1) A city with complex services of sub-regional importance – Oradea, or according to other classifications, a metropolitan center with supra-regional potential, linked by important flows to four large and medium-sized cities, two in the North-West Region (Satu Mare and Zalău), and the others in the West Region (Arad and Timișoara, the latter with regional center status, like Cluj-Napoca). The area of polarization of the municipality of Oradea includes Bihor County, the northern part of Arad County, the southern part of Satu Mare County and the western part of Sălaj County. (2) Two cities with mixed services, of sub-regional importance – Baia Mare and Satu Mare. Baia Mare is linked by a dominant flow to Cluj-Napoca, while Satu Mare is interconnected with Oradea. Both cities have a relatively extensive area of polarization. Thus, the municipality of Baia Mare polarizes, through local synapses, the entire area of Maramureș County, the eastern part of Satu Mare County and the northern part of Sălaj County. The municipality of Satu Mare has an area of polarization that is restricted to the area of the county of the same name. (3) Two cities with mixed services of county importance – Zalău and Sighetu-Marmației. The municipality of Zalău is linked to the higher-level regional center of Cluj-Napoca, while Sighetu-Marmației is linked to the sub-regional center of Baia Mare. The areas of polarization of these urban centers are less extensive, being limited to the territory of the county to which they belong. (4) Three urban centers with zonal influence (Salonta, Carei, Borșa). (5) Eight urban centers with a specialized profile and diffuse influence (Beiuș, Marghita, Săcueni, Valea lui Mihai, Baia Sprie, Vișeu de Sus, Târgu Lăpuș, Șimleu Silvaniei). (6) 17 urban centers with local influence (Aleșd, Nucet, Ștei, Vașcău, Negrești-Oaș, Tășnad, Ardud, Livada, Seini, Șomcuta Mare, Ulmeni, Tăuții Măgheruș, Cavnic, Săliște de Sus, Dragomirești, Cehu Silvaniei and Jibou). (7) Areas where there are no urban centers of economic growth and which are in deep socio-demographic decline: the south of Satu Mare County; the south of Bihor County; the south and south-east of Sălaj County.

In terms of the set of values that make up the aggregate indicator measuring the degree of achievement of sustainable development goals, the counties of Bihor, Satu Mare and Maramureș are in an intermediate position (score 3.81 - 4.46), Sălaj being the county with the lowest score, between 3.17 and 3.80. At the level of the Territorial Administrative Units (TAUs), nine urban centers have scores between 4.07 and 5.32. At the other end of the spectrum, isolated communities without access to urban centers perform poorly (score 2.49 - 3.16). The four counties are also at an average level in terms of the Territorial Development Index, with areas with low scores for development disparities (1.9–2.53) being mainly in the TAUs located along the border with Hungary (CJ Bihor, 2021, pp. 231 - 233).

Furthermore, based on the study published by Dumitru Radu (2011) and the local social development index (IDSL) calculated for each county, we can say that in Bihor County, the development gap between rural areas (IDSL – 52) and urban areas (IDSL – 83) has widened, due to the limited capacity of rural communities to connect to cities of sub-regional and county importance and to take advantage of their polarizing force. This creates an image of medium-to-high developed cities, complemented by that of small towns and villages that are developing in isolation, without the interdependence links specific to local and regional development processes (Bihor C.C., 2021, p. 223). The same situation can be found in Sălaj County, where the IDSL for rural communities is 48 and for urban areas is 83 (Sălaj C.C., 2021, p. 265).

Objectives, questions, and research methods

In the current context, where the Romanian political landscape is in constant flux, the study aims to examine electoral behavior in regions that have experienced socio-economic progress, to identify how regional disparities in welfare can influence electoral preferences, and to highlight the role of socio-economic factors, which are determinants in the growth of sustainable development indicators, in the processes of facilitating political preferences from the perspective of electoral behavior patterns. The case study focuses on Romania, more specifically on four NUTS III areas belonging to the North-West Development Region (Bihor, Satu-Mare, Sălaj and Maramureș), an area that has experienced rapid development over the last two decades. The research questions focus on the results obtained by the two candidates who participated in the second round of the presidential elections on 18 May 2025 in the four counties mentioned above, and are as follows: Q1 – What is the relationship between the stage of development of each of the four counties and the electoral preferences of their residents? Q2 – Does the existence of economic agglomerations in the analyzed areas substantially polarize the vote between urban and rural areas? Q3 – Are the income and the way in which voters in the four counties benefit from education and social support also reflected in the results recorded by each of the two candidates in each region?

To answer the three questions above, the study quantitatively analyses a series of data, reported for the year 2025, which were collected from official sources, published online on the website of the Central Electoral Bureau (CEB) and the Permanent Electoral Authority regarding the results of the second round of the presidential elections on 18 May 2025. Only the data necessary for the case study was recorded by analyzing the pages of the four counties of Bihor, Satu Mare, Sălaj and Maramureș. In addition, the values of the indicators reflecting the development status of the NUTS III regions mentioned above were collected from the official website of the European Union's Eurobarometer (EUROSTAT) and the data published by the National Institute of Statistics (INS) for the 2021 National Census.

Thus, in line with the study published by Kulachai, Lerdtomornsakul and Homyamyen (2023), data available for the North-West development region was collected, which showed high potential to influence the distribution of votes in the second round of the elections on 18 May 2025. The recorded data was reported in relation to the environment of origin, level of education, GDP or income/county, unemployment, employment status and voter turnout. Uncertain (or omitted) data on the quality of life in the four counties, trust in state institutions (at the county level), and the level of well-being were excluded from the analysis. The excluded data, although defined, were not presented conclusively by the NIS. The official statistics were associated with surveys in the North-West development region on social support, based on previous conceptualizations on this topic (Marian, Chirodea and Țoca, 2024).

The statistical data were analyzed with the SPSS program using the variables presented above, as well as how they are associated with the number of votes cast for one of the two candidates (Nicușor Dan versus George Simion). The process was implemented using the Bravais-Pearson correlation as a statistical measure that evaluates the strength and direction of the linear relationship between variables. The study also quantifies how the data sets from the four counties in the North-West development region vary, showing that when one increases, the other tends to increase or has no clear relationship.

Results and discussion

A preliminary comparison of data collected from official sources reveals that Nicușor Dan is the winner in all four counties analyzed, with an average of 60.13% of the votes in his favor. A more in-depth statistical analysis reveals a set of associations between a group of variables considered relevant and the distribution of votes in the second round for the two candidates. The Bravais-Pearson correlation coefficient between the environment of origin and electoral preferences indicates a strong association between rural areas and votes for candidate Nicușor Dan ($r=.965$; $p<.02$), while in urban areas the association is highly significant for candidate George Simion ($r=.981$; $p<.01$) in the four counties analyzed (Table 1). Therefore, it is evident that Nicușor Dan was the preferred candidate for well over 60% of voters in rural areas. Greater differences between candidates in small and isolated localities, and smaller ones in larger or peri-urban communes, are only local nuances caused by various micro-regional factors (the influence of local political and cultural elites, the structure of the population according to ethnicity and religion, the influence of the diaspora on those remaining in the community, the proximity of a major urban center, etc.).

Table 1. Correlation matrix of factors with the potential to influence elections.

Variables analyzed		Votes for George Simion	Votes for Nicușor Dan	Voter turnout
Background	Rural	.828	.965*	.977*
	Urban	.981*	.880	.973*
Educational level	Students	.959*	.927	.994**
	Higher education	.958*	.927	.994**
	Post-secondary	.932	.982*	.977*
	High school	.802	.906	.967*
	Secondary	.949*	.968*	.958*
GDP / income County		.297	.424	.576
Unemployment		-.808	-.389	-.619
Occupational status		-.045	-.299	-.389
Voter turnout		.924	.947	---

Note: * indicates the correlation coefficient is statistically significant at $p<0.05$. ** $p<0.01$.

For the statistical result obtained from processing the data collected from urban areas, the analysis was supplemented with the data in Table 2. Thus, it can be easily observed that as the urban pole becomes less important in the Developed Region to which the four counties belong, the electorate's preferences shift from the progressive candidate (Nicușor Dan) to the populist-sovereignist candidate (George Simion), as large cities are usually important urban centers at the sub-regional, county or local level. The exception is the eight urban centers with a specialized

profile and diffuse influence, where the focus on a particular type of economic activity has been an advantage in local development processes, which has been positively noted by voters. However, the association recorded for George Simion can be explained by the fact that he won the electorate in the rest of the small towns, mostly in Maramureş County, which have a local economy based mainly on tourism and whose authorities have no solutions for improving sustainable development or territorial cohesion indicators.

Table 2. Voting results in cities according to the type of urban development pole.

Type of urban development hub	Votes for Nicușor Dan (average %)	Votes for George Simion (average %)
Urban center, complex services, sub-regional importance	73.26	26.74
Urban centers, mixed services, sub-regional importance	68.51	31.49
Cities of county importance	60.86	39.14
Urban centers with regional influence	60.51	39.49
Urban centers, specialized profile, diffuse influence	63.83	36.1
Urban centers with local influence	53.25	46.7

Furthermore, if we overlay the map of the territorial development index recorded in each TAU in the four counties (MRDPA, 2014, p. 115) over the map showing the results obtained by the two candidates, we can see that in the localities on the border with Hungary in Bihor and Satu Mare and in several others where the score for development disparities is between 1.9 and 2.53, the electorate's preferences leaned towards the progressive candidate, Nicușor Dan.

If we consider another indicator of regional economic progress, namely GDP or income in each county analyzed, statistically, we cannot identify any relevant associations for the votes cast by voters for the two candidates in the second round in May 2025. Similarly, the unemployment recorded and reported for the four counties in the North-West Development Region does not significantly influence electoral preferences. Moreover, at the occupational level, we do not find any statistical associations with the preference for one of the candidates, nor with the turnout of residents. The latter, however, is strongly associated with votes cast for candidate Nicușor Dan ($r=.947$; $p<.05$), while votes cast for candidate George Simion are in an area of statistically significant trends ($r=.924$; $p<.07$). In addition, the analysis of invalid votes recorded in the minutes published by the Central Election Bureau for the counties of Bihor, Sălaj, Satu Mare and Maramureş does not indicate a statistically significant correlation for any of the candidates in the second round of the elections.

Among the social factors that are decisive for regional development processes, the level of education has a significant impact on the voting decisions of voters in the four counties. In line with other research suggesting that people with a high level of education are more likely to vote (Evans and Andersen, 2006), we find that this indicator, together with the perception of social support, is among the strongest factors influencing participation in political life. The results obtained highlight the fact that voters in the areas analysed give priority to populist or sovereigntist political issues, a trend reflected in the votes cast for candidate George Simion. Thus, the votes for candidate George Simion come from students ($r=.959$; $p<.04$), voters with higher education ($r=.958$; $p<.04$) and those with secondary education ($r=.949$; $p<.05$), while a strong positive association of votes cast for candidate Nicușor Dan is recorded among voters with post-secondary education ($r=.982$; $p<.01$) and secondary education ($r=.968$; $p<.03$). In the case of voter turnout in line with our expectations, the coefficients recorded are strongly associated with the voters' background and educational level (Table 1).

Conclusions

In Romania in 2025, transition and development processes are intertwined, often increasing the pace of progress, especially in the economic dimension. This phenomenon also has negative social and economic consequences: certain vulnerable population groups are marginalized and segregated, and at the territorial level, it generates large cleavages in the development of NUTS III regions and TAU-s (Basarabă, 2015: 70). In this context, the quality and capacity of local or national decision-makers to achieve good governance are very important not only in the operationalization of development strategies, but also in the way people perceive their own well-being and the socio-economic progress of the community to which they belong.

The analysis of the data collected in this study highlights the fact that there is a direct influence between the socio-economic context expressed through a series of indicators that reflect the stage of development processes and the way in which the electorate residing in the four counties analyzed expressed their preference for the progressive independent candidate, Nicușor Dan, or for the populist-sovereignist candidate, George Simion (Q1).

The results obtained by the candidates in the second round of voting, beyond the political discourse of each, emphasize that other factors also shape electoral behavior in urban and rural areas. While for rural communities, statistical data processing confirmed expectations, in cities, where the cost of living is often high, voters may feel disillusioned with the political system, which makes them prefer populist or sovereignist candidates. Our research has shown that this phenomenon did not manifest itself in urban centers with sub-regional influence, but rather in those with local influence. One of the reasons for this is the way in which residents of small towns perceive communication with local authorities and their efforts to raise living standards and involve citizens in the decision-making process. In addition, the highly significant association for George Simion in urban areas confirms the hypothesis that voters with higher education tend to be more involved in political activities when they are disillusioned (Acibotăriței, 2024) and that young people, who represent a significant part of the urban population and a vulnerable population group, are less motivated to vote, partly because of the perception that their vote does not matter. This perception may be amplified by political campaigns that fail to address the specific needs and concerns of young people, such as the use of digital platforms, climate change or economic issues (Stoica, 2025). Creating a more responsible civic culture or implementing governance policies are tools that have already demonstrated their potential to improve the active participation of the electorate in the democratic process (Siminiuc, 2024), with cities with transparent and responsible public administrations also having a higher number of active voters. Therefore, there are differences between the preferences of voters residing in communes or cities, which are more visible in the case of small cities (Q2).

Contrary to the opinions of other researchers, the analysis of associations in the four counties does not lead to statistical relevance of the coefficients between income and voter turnout or decisive preference for one of the two candidates. In other words, regardless of income, voters do not have an obvious predisposition towards a sovereignist or progressive neoliberal orientation. However, another fundamental aspect highlighted by our study is the role that education plays in shaping voter preferences. This determining factor in development processes gives individuals/voters the ability to think critically, access information and gain a deep understanding of real economic and social issues, which can influence their voting decisions and major political preferences. Equally, highly educated voters may be dissatisfied with the lack of vision of local authorities regarding solutions to raise the standard of living and well-being of residents. Furthermore, if these results are correlated with the low

perception of social support among intellectuals, at an implicit level (Marian, Chirodea and Țoca, 2024), this hypothetically generates a selection of voting options contrary to the accepted scientific opinion on neoliberal progressivism. The study highlights that people with a higher level of education prioritized different political issues, voting for George Simion, compared to those with a lower level of education who expressed their preference for Nicușor Dan, regardless of their income. In conclusion, income did not play a significant role in shaping voting decisions, but rather adherence to a movement that indicates a perception of implicit social support for the decisions made – Q3 (Marian, Chirodea and Țoca, 2024).

In conclusion, the results obtained by the two candidates in the second round of the presidential elections on 18 May 2025 are not just electoral statistics, but a barometer of the average stage of development reached by the communities in the four NUTS III regions analyzed. If in 2014, Professor Dumitru Sandu classified them as "a group of counties of maximum electoral controversy, with an equality of options for Iohannis and Ponta", following the preference expressed by voters for Nicușor Dan (average percentage of 60.13% favorable votes), we can classify these areas as moderately developed counties, with progressive neoliberal tendencies similar to those of the "highly developed counties of Transylvania" (Sandu, 2014). Among the main motivations for voting, according to the classification made by Basarabă (2015), were: (1) the sanctioning of local authorities by disappointed voters and the mobilization of preferences towards sovereigntist electoral offers, which is compounded by voters who consistently express their opposition to the government in the case of the majority of voters in small towns and a small proportion of those in large cities; (2) the identification of local symbolic landmarks in rural areas and elites in large cities with modernization, progress and Europeanisation, alongside loyalty to a party.

In the broader context of the 2024 and 2025 elections, we believe it is important for decision-makers and political actors to recognize the importance of these variables for the health of a democracy and to develop tailored strategies to stimulate sustainable and inclusive development and a stimulating environment that encourages participatory democracy.

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